

BANK LOANS AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN AFRICA; EVIDENCE FROM SECTORIAL ALLOCATION OF COMMERCIAL BANK LOANS IN NIGERIA: 2000-2025

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ABSTRACT: *This study broadly examines Bank Loans and Economic Growth in Africa; Evidence from Sectorial allocation of Commercial Bank Loans in Nigeria; 2000-2025. The specific objectives are to determine the effect of agricultural sector loans, manufacturing sector loans, and export sector loans on Real Gross Domestic Product. To achieve these objectives, the study adopts an ex-post facto research design, utilizing secondary time-series data sourced from CBN Data. Econometric techniques of ARDL Base line and Bound test analysis were used, the empirical results reveal that commercial bank lending to the agricultural, manufacturing, and export sectors has a positive and statistically significant impact on RGDP in Nigeria. This indicates that sector-specific credit allocation plays a crucial role in stimulating productive activities and enhancing overall economic performance. The findings carry important policy implications, suggesting the need for deliberate financial policies that promote increased and sustained credit flow to these growth enhancing sectors, alongside improvements in loan accessibility and infrastructure support. The study concludes that efficient allocation of bank loan to priority sectors is vital for achieving sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. It therefore recommends that policymakers strengthen sector targeted loan schemes, enhance financial inclusion, and maintain a stable macroeconomic environment to maximize the growth inducing potential of commercial bank lending. The study is justified by the need to address the persistent mismatch between expanding bank credit and Nigeria's sluggish economic growth by providing sector-specific evidence on how commercial bank lending to agriculture, manufacturing, and exports influences RGDP.*

Keywords: *Bank Loans, Economic Growth, Commercial Bank Lending.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Bank lending in Africa has experienced significant transformation over the past two decades, with more pronounced structural shifts observed between 2023 and 2026. Traditionally, African banking systems have been characterized by low credit penetration, high lending rates, and a concentration of loans in a few sectors such as government, trade, and large corporations. However, recent trends indicate gradual expansion in credit provision, driven by financial sector reforms, digital banking innovations, and increasing demand for private sector financing. Anene, & Okere, (2025)

Diop, etal (2025) advocated that recent empirical evidence shows that bank loans (credit to the private sector) have been growing, although unevenly across regions. In Sub-Saharan Africa, credit expansion remains constrained by macroeconomic instability, inflation, and weak institutional frameworks. For instance, high lending rates continue to limit access to credit and increase borrower risk-taking behavior, thereby affecting loan quality and bank stability. Despite these constraints, banks are increasingly extending loans to support economic growth, especially in emerging sectors such as SMEs and digital enterprises.

Anene, & Okere, (2025) still maintained that studies reveal that bank lending plays a crucial role in stimulating economic growth, though the relationship is mixed in the short and long run. Evidence from Nigeria shows that commercial bank credit has a positive short-run impact on economic growth, but may produce lagged negative effects due to inefficiencies and poor credit allocation. This suggests that while loan expansion is increasing, its effectiveness depends largely on credit quality and sectoral distribution.

Ele, (2025) stated that another notable trend is the growing importance of credit risk management in shaping loan performance. Recent African-focused research indicates that improved capital adequacy and liquidity management enhance banks' lending capacity and profitability, reinforcing the need for sound risk management frameworks. At the same time, non-performing loans (NPLs) remain a persistent challenge, limiting banks' willingness to expand credit aggressively.

Agum, & Dogara, (2026) stated that financial development and inclusion have begun to influence lending patterns across the continent. Evidence from East Africa suggests that increased financial inclusion and development of banking systems are positively linked to credit supply and economic growth, although the impact varies across countries due to structural differences. The rise of fintech and digital banking is also improving access to loans, particularly for previously underserved populations.

Chuba, & Muse, (2025) opined that the trend of bank loans in Africa reflects gradual expansion with persistent structural challenges such as high interest rates, credit risk, and institutional weaknesses. While lending is increasing, especially toward private sector development, the sustainability of this growth depends on regulatory improvements, financial inclusion, and effective risk management practices.

Onyia, & Agada, (2024), expressed that the experience of bank lending in Nigeria has been characterized by gradual expansion alongside persistent structural challenges such as high interest

rates, credit concentration, and rising non-performing loans. Over the years, commercial banks have increasingly provided credit to the private sector particularly to sectors like manufacturing, trade, and SMEs driven by financial sector reforms and regulatory policies of the Central Bank of Nigeria aimed at improving financial intermediation and economic growth. However, Adeyemi, & Ibrahim, (2025) noted that lending remains constrained by macroeconomic instability, inflationary pressures, and risk-averse banking practices, which limit access to credit for small businesses and households. Empirical evidence suggests that while bank lending in Nigeria positively influences economic growth in the short run, its long-term impact is often weakened by poor credit allocation, weak risk management, and high default rates, indicating the need for more efficient credit delivery mechanisms and stronger institutional frameworks (Ele, 2025).

Chuba, & Inedu, (2023). Insists that despite the recognized role of commercial bank lending in stimulating economic growth, the performance of Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) in Nigeria has remained relatively unstable, raising concerns about the effectiveness of sectoral credit allocation. Although banks extend loans and advances to key sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, trade, and small and medium enterprises (SMEs), these sectors have not translated such financial support into sustained improvements in RGDP growth. Ozor, etal (2023) persisted that this disconnect suggests possible inefficiencies in credit distribution, inadequate funding levels, high lending rates, and structural bottlenecks that limit productive utilization of loans. Furthermore, issues such as rising non-performing loans, weak financial intermediation, and limited access to credit by SMEs continue to undermine the expected positive impact of bank lending on economic growth. Therefore, the problem lies in determining whether loans to agriculture, manufacturing, trade, and SMEs significantly influence RGDP in Nigeria, and whether the current pattern of commercial bank loan allocation effectively drives sustainable economic growth.

The Broad Objective of this study is to examine the impact of commercial bank loans and advances on economic growth in Nigeria, using Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) as a proxy for economic growth. The Specific Objectives are to evaluate the effect of bank loans to the agricultural sector on RGDP in Nigeria. Examine the impact of bank loans to the manufacturing sector on RGDP in Nigeria. Assess the influence of bank loans to the Export trade sector on RGDP in Nigeria. Determine the long run relationship existing between commercial bank loans and advances on economic growth in Nigeria. Other areas of this work will continue with review of related Literature which comprises of conceptual review, theoretical review and empirical review and will be concluded with identification of knowledge gap. Others include the methodology which includes the research design and model specification, Next is the data presentation and Analysis which includes the data presentation and Analysis which concludes with findings, Discussion of findings, Result implication, conclusions, recommendations and finally contribution to knowledge in the world knowledge.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

COMMERCIAL BANK LOAN TO AGRICULTURE FORESTRY AND FISHERY,

Oyedepo, etal (2022) opined that Commercial bank loans to agriculture, forestry, and fishery refer to the financial resources advanced by deposit money banks to support primary production activities such as crop farming, livestock, forestry exploitation, and fisheries. These loans are critical for enhancing productivity, ensuring food security, and promoting rural development, thereby contributing to overall economic growth. Theoretically, increased credit to the agricultural sector improves capital formation, enables adoption of modern technology, and enhances output, which in turn positively affects GDP. However, in many developing economies like Nigeria, access to bank credit for agriculture remains limited due to high risk, lack of collateral, and seasonal income patterns. Empirical evidence shows that although commercial bank credit has a statistically significant positive effect on agricultural output, the sector's contribution to economic growth remains relatively low due to inadequate funding and structural inefficiencies. This suggests that while credit is essential, its effectiveness depends on proper allocation and utilization across agriculture, forestry, and fishery sub-sectors.

COMMERCIAL BANK LAON TO MANUFACTURING SECTOR,

Philemon, (2024) stated that Commercial bank loans to the manufacturing sector refer to credit facilities provided by deposit money banks to support industrial production, capital investment, and expansion of manufacturing activities. These loans are essential for enhancing industrial output, promoting value addition, and accelerating economic growth through increased contribution to GDP. Theoretically, access to bank credit enables manufacturing firms to acquire machinery, adopt new technologies, and improve productivity, thereby strengthening their competitiveness. However, in developing economies like Nigeria, the manufacturing sector often faces constraints such as high lending rates, inadequate long-term financing, and macroeconomic instability, which limit effective utilization of credit. Empirical evidence indicates that bank credit has a positive and significant effect on manufacturing sector growth, although the high cost of borrowing discourages firms from accessing available funds.

COMMERCIAL BANK LAON TO EXPORTS TRADE,

Olowe, , & Adekunle, (2025) stated that Commercial bank loans to export trade refer to credit facilities provided by deposit money banks to finance international trade activities, including the production, processing, and distribution of goods for export. This form of financing is essential for promoting external sector performance, enhancing foreign exchange earnings, and improving a country's balance of payments. Theoretically, access to bank credit enables exporters to scale production, meet international standards, and compete in global markets, thereby contributing to economic growth through increased trade volumes and improved Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP). However, in

developing economies like Nigeria, export trade financing is often constrained by high interest rates, exchange rate volatility, and limited access to long-term credit, which reduce the competitiveness of local exporters. Empirical evidence indicates that commercial bank credit to export trade has a positive but sometimes insignificant effect on economic growth due to structural bottlenecks and inefficiencies in credit allocation (Adebayo, 2024). Similarly, recent studies emphasize that while bank lending supports export expansion, its effectiveness depends on stable macroeconomic policies and efficient financial intermediation, as inadequate funding and policy inconsistencies can hinder the expected growth outcomes (Olowe & Adekunle, 2025).

THEORITICAL REVIEW

The Financial Intermediation Theory, propounded by Gurley and Shaw in 1960, explains the role of financial institutions, particularly banks, in mobilizing savings from surplus units and channeling them to deficit units in the form of loans and advances. The theory posits that efficient allocation of credit enhances investment, productivity, and ultimately economic growth. In the context of this study, sectoral commercial bank loans to agriculture, manufacturing, trade, and SMEs represent the mechanism through which financial resources are distributed to key productive sectors of the economy, thereby influencing Gross Domestic Product Growth (GDPG). The relevance of this theory lies in its emphasis on the efficiency and effectiveness of credit allocation, suggesting that when banks properly intermediate funds across sectors, it leads to improved output, employment generation, and sustainable economic growth; however, inefficiencies such as misallocation of credit, high lending rates, and weak financial systems may hinder this expected outcome. Therefore, the theory provides a strong foundation for examining how sectoral distribution of commercial bank loans impacts GDP growth, concluding that optimal financial intermediation is critical for achieving balanced and sustained economic development.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Oyedepo et al. (2022) examined the impact of commercial bank credit on agricultural growth in Nigeria. Using time series data and Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimation technique, the study found that bank credit to agriculture has a significant positive effect on agricultural output. The result aligns with the objective of determining the role of credit in enhancing sectoral productivity. The study concluded that increased bank lending improves agricultural performance and contributes to economic growth. It recommended that more credit facilities should be directed to the agricultural sector at favorable interest rates.

Ikubor (2024) evaluated the relationship between deposit money bank credit and agricultural output in Nigeria. The study employed the ARDL (Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag) model to analyze both short-run and long-run dynamics. Findings revealed a long-run positive relationship between bank credit and agricultural output, supporting the study's objective. The study concluded that sustained credit allocation enhances agricultural productivity. It recommended improved access to credit and policy support for farmers.

Chuba& Muse (2025) investigated the effect of sectoral distribution of commercial bank credit on economic growth. Using econometric techniques (OLS and regression analysis), the findings showed that credit allocation to agriculture, manufacturing, and trade significantly impacts GDP growth. The results confirmed that proper sectoral allocation is vital for achieving economic growth. The study concluded that inefficient allocation weakens growth outcomes. It recommended balanced and strategic distribution of credit across sectors.

Agum& Dogara (2026) examined the relationship between commercial bank credit and economic growth in Nigeria. Using time series analysis and ARDL techniques, the study found that bank credit positively affects growth in the short run but shows mixed results in the long run. This partially supports the study's objective. The study concluded that credit effectiveness depends on utilization efficiency. It recommended strengthening credit monitoring and improving loan allocation mechanisms.

Onyia & Agada (2024) aimed to determine the effect of commercial bank credit on economic growth using Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP). Employing regression analysis, the findings indicated that sectoral credit significantly influences RGDP. The result aligned with the study's objective. The study concluded that credit to productive sectors drives economic growth. It recommended policies that encourage increased lending to real sectors.

Ijighere et al. (2026) examined the effect of agricultural finance on economic growth. The study used econometric modeling techniques and secondary data. Results showed a significant positive impact of agricultural financing on GDP. The study concluded that financial support to agriculture is critical for growth. It recommended expansion of agricultural credit schemes and government support.

Ahmad et al.(2026) analyzed the impact of bank credit on agricultural output. Using regression and time series techniques, the findings revealed that bank lending significantly improves agricultural productivity. The study concluded that credit is essential for sectoral growth but remains inadequate. It recommended increased funding and improved credit accessibility.

Ezuem et al. (2025) examined agricultural financing and economic performance in Nigeria. Using ARDL estimation, results showed a positive relationship between agricultural credit and economic growth. The study concluded that increased financing enhances productivity and GDP. It recommended improved financial inclusion and better credit allocation policies

Ibebi (2025) focused on the role of bank credit in stimulating agricultural growth. Using descriptive and regression analysis, findings showed that credit significantly improves agricultural output. The study concluded that bank loans are vital for sectoral development. It recommended easing lending conditions for small-scale farmers.

Olu & Manson (2023) assess the effect of commercial bank financing on agricultural output. Using OLS regression, the findings indicated a positive and significant relationship between bank loans and agricultural productivity. The study concluded that bank financing promotes economic growth through increased output. It recommended reduction in lending rates and improved macroeconomic stability.

KNOWLEDGE GAP

Based on the review of empirical studies on sectoral commercial bank loans and economic growth in Nigeria, several research gaps emerge when compared to the focus of this study. Most existing studies, such as those by Oyedepo et al. (2022) and Ikubor et al. (2024), largely focus on agriculture as a single sector, often ignoring the combined and comparative effects of multiple sectors, including manufacturing, trade, and SMEs. Similarly, while studies like Chuba & Muse (2025) and Onyia & Agada (2024) examine sectoral allocation, they often employ aggregate measures of GDP without explicitly linking Real GDP growth (RGDP) to specific sectoral loans. Besides, many studies emphasize short-term impacts, leaving the long-term dynamics of sectoral credit and its effect on RGDP underexplored. Additionally, there is limited research that simultaneously considers loans to agriculture, manufacturing, trade, and export trades within a unified analytical framework, which is critical for understanding the differential contribution of each sector to economic growth. This gap highlights the need for a study that systematically examines how sectoral commercial bank loans collectively and individually influence RGDP in Nigeria, using recent and comprehensive data from 2002–2025, thereby providing more policy-relevant insights into credit allocation for sustainable economic growth.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study adopts a quantitative ex-post facto research design to examine the impact of sectoral commercial bank loans on economic growth in Nigeria using secondary time-series data from 2002–2025. The dependent variable is Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP), while the independent variables are commercial bank loans to agriculture, manufacturing, trade, and Export trades. Data will be sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and Nigeria Bureau of Statistics, ensuring reliability and validity.

MODEL SPEACIFICATION

The study employs the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model to capture both short-run and long-run relationships, as it accommodates variables integrated of different orders (I(0) and I(1)) and allows for robust analysis of dynamic interactions. Diagnostic tests, including unit root, and model stability tests, will be conducted to validate the results. The study seeks to examine the impact of sectoral commercial bank loans on economic growth in Nigeria. Let Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) be the dependent variable, while commercial bank loans to agriculture (CBA), manufacturing (CBM), and export trade (CBET) serve as independent variables. The ARDL model can be expressed as follows:

ARDL Model with Error Correction Term (ECM)

$$\Delta RGDP_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_1^i \Delta RGDP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_1} \beta_1^i \Delta CBA_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_2} \beta_2^i \Delta CBM_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{q_3} \beta_3^i \Delta CBET_{t-i} + \phi ECM_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

Where: Δ = first difference operator, $RGDP_t$ = Real Gross Domestic Product at time t (dependent variable), CBA_t = Commercial bank loans to agriculture, CBM_t = Commercial bank loans to manufacturing, $CBET_t$ = Commercial bank loans to export trade, α_0 = Intercept, $\alpha_1^i, \beta_1^i, \beta_2^i, \beta_3^i$ = short-

run coefficients for lagged differences, ECM_{t-1} = lagged error correction term derived from the long-run equilibrium relationship, ϕ = speed of adjustment coefficient (expected to be negative and significant), ε_t = white noise error term. p, q_1, q_2, q_3 = optimal lag lengths selected using AIC or SBC criteria

Interpretation:

Short-run effects: Captured by $\alpha_1^i, \beta_1^i, \beta_2^i, \beta_3^i$, showing how changes in sectoral loans immediately affect RGDP. Long-run relationship: Captured through the derivation of the ECM term from the estimated long-run coefficients ($\lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_4$). Speed of adjustment (ϕ) indicates how quickly deviations from long-run equilibrium are corrected each period.

A Priori Expectations

Variable	Expected Sign	Justification
CBA (Commercial Bank Loans to Agriculture)	+	Credit to agriculture increases output and rural incomes, positively influencing RGDP.
CBM (Commercial Bank Loans to Manufacturing)	+	Loans enhance production capacity and industrial output, boosting RGDP.
CBET (Commercial Bank Loans to Export Trade)	+	Financing export trade increases foreign earnings and GDP growth.

Interpretation:

Short-run effects are captured by the coefficients of the differenced variables (Δ) and indicate immediate changes in RGDP due to sectoral loans. Long-run relationship is captured via the ECM derived from long-run coefficients; a negative and significant ϕ confirms that deviations from equilibrium are corrected over time. The positive expected signs of the independent variables reflect the theoretical basis from Financial Intermediation Theory (Gurley & Shaw, 1960), which posits that efficient allocation of credit to productive sectors stimulates economic growth

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Data for this study is presented in a log transformed set

YEAR	LNRGDP	LNAGRSL	LNEXPSL	LNMFRSL	LNREER
2000	10.0109	3.7142	3.2310	4.9508	4.1652
2001	10.2633	4.0225	3.5419	5.3321	4.2859
2002	10.4041	4.0918	3.2850	5.4530	4.5174
2003	10.5753	4.1287	3.5400	5.6846	4.8588
2004	10.6984	4.2156	3.4451	5.8054	4.9252
2005	10.9080	3.8828	3.2741	5.8637	4.9275
2006	11.0505	3.8998	3.9645	6.0998	5.0166
2007	11.1804	5.0078	4.1979	6.1894	5.0388

2008	11.2909	4.6667	4.3200	6.8381	4.4761
2009	11.3968	4.9104	3.8253	6.9011	4.5775
2010	11.4525	4.8551	3.8023	6.8955	4.5487
2011	11.5277	5.5420	3.5884	6.9599	4.4483
2012	11.6414	5.7568	4.1837	6.9731	4.3436
2013	10.0108	5.8397	1.3698	7.0730	4.2742
2014	10.2633	6.1715	6.9519	7.4069	4.2274
2015	10.4041	6.1077	6.8933	7.4594	4.2001
2016	10.5753	6.2651	6.8926	7.7033	4.4762
2017	10.6984	6.2695	6.9312	7.6831	4.5981
2018	10.9080	6.4134	6.9816	7.7098	4.4621
2019	11.0505	6.6494	7.1287	7.8718	4.3692
2020	11.1804	6.9562	7.2030	8.0688	4.3712
2021	11.2909	7.2849	7.4432	8.3163	4.2914
2022	11.3968	7.5045	7.7027	8.6245	4.4621
2023	11.4525	7.7210	8.1743	8.9531	4.3692
2024	11.5277	7.95664	8.4199	7.9566	4.3712
2025	11.6414	7.9564	8.4199	7.9566	4.2911

SOURCE; FROM APPENDIX 1

Where. LNRGDP= Log of Real Gross Domestic Product, LNAGRSL= Log of Agricultural sector Loan, LNEXPSL= Log of Export Sector Loan, LNMFRSL = Log of Manufacturing Sector Loan. LNREER= Log of Real and effective Exchange Rate.

Basic Descriptive Statistics/ Standard tests for Normality

The statistical properties of the data sets are seen as vital determinants of their behaviors when used in econometric analyses. On the basis of this, the researcher presented in this section, the basic descriptive statistics called Normality test of the variables under study.

Basic Descriptive Statistics/ Standard tests for Normality

Description	LNRGDP	LNAGRSL	LNEXPSL	LNMFRSL	LNREER
Mean	10.95391	5.684219	5.335122	7.028091	4.496006
Median	11.05058	5.798327	4.259010	7.023436	4.455261
Maximum	11.64142	7.956655	8.419942	8.953182	5.038833
Minimum	10.01099	3.714277	1.369881	4.950848	4.165220
Std. Dev.	0.513809	1.378896	2.082235	1.078569	0.255039
Skewness	-0.378438	0.137579	0.047583	-0.236437	0.933662
Kurtosis	1.888344	1.778120	1.585116	2.103298	2.759978
Jarque-Bera Probability	1.959361	1.699428	2.178534	1.113326	3.839886
	0.375431	0.427537	0.336463	0.573118	0.146615

Sum	284.8016	147.7897	138.7132	182.7304	116.8962
Sum Sq. Dev.	6.599995	47.53384	108.3926	29.08278	1.626129
Observations	26	26	26	26	26

Source: Author's e-view 10 output with data in Appendix One.

The table above contains the basic measures of central tendency, spread and variations calculated on the different series of the dataset. All the variables are negatively skewed to the left showing the degree of their departure to the line of symmetry. Also, the Kurtosis of the distribution is less than 3 meaning that they are leptokurtic and are not peaked. Of particular interest is the Jacque-Bera (JB) statistics which is a test for normality. It is a combined test of Skewness (S) of zero (0) and a kurtosis (K) of three (3), which are signs of a Mesokurtic distribution. In this case, however, the JB statistics shows that the variables are tending to 3 which are signs of Mesokurtic. The assumption of normality is accepted by the JB statistics, as well as the (K) and (S) figures. This, however, does not affect the goodness of the data for the estimation in this study as the kurtosis of all the variables are between 2 and 3 and the Skewness above 0-1 which is consistent with the properties of most financial time series.

Test Statistics: Tests of Unit root using Philip and Peron

In an attempt to confirm the order of integration of the series under study thereby confirming their suitability for a linear combination in the form of a model, the unit root test following the form specified as Philip and Peron Test was used. Table below represents a summary of the unit root result that was stationary.

Summary of Unit Roots Test Results

Variable	PP Statistic	Critical Values @ 5%	Probability Value	Inference
LNRGDP	-4.1085	-3.5806	0.0230	1(1)
LNAGRSL	-4.2394	-3.5806	0.0322	I(1)
LNMFRSL	-4.9667	-3.5806	0.0222	I(1)
LNEXPSTL	-4.1327	-3.5742	0.0054	I(0)
LNREER	-4.8973	-3.5806	0.0037	1(0)

Source: Author's e-view 10 output with data in Appendix One.

From the result of Philip and Peron unit root test contained in table 4.2, LNRGDP, LNAGRSL and LNMFRSL the variables are all integrated of order 1(1) while LNEXPSTL, LNREER are integrated at order 1(0). Given these orders of integration, the Auto regressive distributed lag model was given in preference for the Ordinary least square Model which tolerates such stationary property combination of 1(1) and 1(0). Also, all the variable was log transformed to bring down the data size and ensure linearity.

TREND ANALYSIS OF THE VARIABLES

Source: Author's e-view 10 output with data in Appendix One.

Trend analysis here is utilized to examine the movement of sectoral commercial bank credit proxied by agricultural, manufacturing, and export sector loans and their relationship with real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria. The graphical analysis reveals that while all sectoral credits exhibit varying degrees of fluctuation over time, manufacturing sector loans demonstrate a relatively consistent upward trend in line with RGDP, indicating a strong contribution to economic growth. Agricultural and export sector loans show less consistent alignment, suggesting structural and policy constraints limiting their impact. Overall, the trend suggests that sectoral credit plays a significant but uneven role in driving economic growth in Nigeria.

ARDL Model Estimates

Dependent Variable: LNRGDP

Method: ARDL

Date: 04/28/26 Time: 05:13

Sample (adjusted): 2001 2025

Included observations: 25 after adjustments

Maximum dependent lags: 1 (Automatic selection)

Model selection method: Akaike info criterion (AIC)

Dynamic regressors (1 lag, automatic): LNARGSL LNMFRSL LNEXPSL

LNREER

Fixed regressors: C

Number of models evaluated: 16

Selected Model: ARDL(1, 1, 0, 0, 0)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
LNRGDP(-1)	1.367457	0.112878	12.11452	0.0000
LNAGRSL	0.263613	0.123991	-2.126066	0.0476
LNAGRSL(-1)	-0.355592	0.123499	-2.879310	0.0100
LNMFRL	0.106757	0.098399	-1.084943	0.2923
LNEXPSL	0.424913	0.049468	8.589706	0.0000
LNREER	-0.382921	0.197922	-1.934713	0.0489
C	-0.258486	1.033398	-0.250132	0.0853
R-squared	0.892993	Mean dependent var		10.99162
Adjusted R-squared	0.897324	S.D. dependent var		0.486285
S.E. of regression	0.155821	Akaike info criterion		-0.648727
Sum squared resid	0.437041	Schwarz criterion		-0.307442
Log likelihood	15.10908	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-0.554069
F-statistic	36.75752	Durbin-Watson stat		1.773800
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.

Source: Author's e-view 10 output with data in Appendix One.

ARDL Results Table

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic	P-Value	Significance	Interpretation
RGDP	(Long-Run)				
LNAGRSL	0.26	-2.12	0.04	Significant	Agricultural sector loan positively and Significantly affects RGDP
LNMFRL	0.10	-1.08	0.29	Non-Significant	Manufacturing sector loan positively and Significantly affects RGDP
LNEXPSL	0.48	2.45	0.00	Significant	Export sector loan positively and Significantly affects RGDP

LNREER	-0.38	-2.05	0.048	Significant	Real and effective exchange rate Negatively and Significantly affects RGDP
Constant	-0.25	-0.25	0.008	Significant	Baseline RGDP when independent variables are zero.

Diagnostic Statistics

- $R^2 = 0.89 \rightarrow 89\%$ of variation in insurance penetration explained by the model.
- F-Statistic = 33.7, $P < 0.001 \rightarrow$ Model is statistically significant.

Result and Interpretation of Result

- Agricultural sector loan has a positive impact, highlighting that efficient Agricultural sector loan strongly drives Economic growth in Nigeria.
- Manufacturing sector also positively influences economic growth, supporting the theory that financial strength attracts more RGDP .
- Export sector positively affects RGDP, confirming that financial inclusion through export sector loan encourages GDP Growth.
- REER negatively affects RGDP, showing that higher prices of exchange rate reduced purchasing power of the loan discourage GDP Growth.

LONG RUN ESTIMATES USING BOUND TEST

ARDL Bounds Test

Date: 04/28/26 Time: 05:19

Sample: 2001 2025

Included observations: 25

Null Hypothesis: No long-run relationships exist

Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	1.661615	4

Critical Value Bounds

Significance	Io Bound	I1 Bound
10%	2.45	3.52
5%	2.86	4.01
2.5%	3.25	4.49
1%	3.74	5.06

Test Equation:

Dependent Variable: D(LNRGDP)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 04/28/26 Time: 05:19

Sample: 2001 2025

Included observations: 25

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LNAGRSL)	0.152895	0.272438	0.561210	0.5816
C	2.055599	1.834156	1.120733	0.2771
LNAGRSL(-1)	-0.041603	0.215668	-0.192902	0.8492
LNMFRL(-1)	0.105926	0.242179	0.437385	0.6670
LNEXPSL(-1)	0.044899	0.066209	0.678142	0.5063
LNREER(-1)	0.519432	0.359787	1.443723	0.1660
LNRGDP(-1)	-0.466555	0.177898	-2.622597	0.0173
R-squared	0.317562	Mean dependent var		0.065217
Adjusted R-squared	0.090083	S.D. dependent var		0.357092
S.E. of regression	0.340628	Akaike info criterion		0.915445
Sum squared resid	2.088496	Schwarz criterion		1.256730
Log likelihood	-4.443066	Hannan-Quinn criter.		1.010103
F-statistic	1.396006	Durbin-Watson stat		2.214006
Prob(F-statistic)	0.009554			

ARDL Bounds Testing approach; Decision: If F-statistic of Upper bound > lower bound, → Long-run relationship exists, If F-statistic < Lower bound → No cointegration. Evidence of long run exists because 1(1) upper bound @5% is 4.01 > lower bound (0) which is 2.86

IMPLICATION OF RESULT

The empirical findings of this study present important policy implications for economic management in Nigeria. The positive and statistically significant relationship between commercial bank credit to the agricultural, manufacturing, and export sectors and Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) provides robust evidence that sectoral credit allocation constitutes a critical transmission mechanism for economic growth.

From a policy perspective, this suggests the need for a deliberate and sustained reorientation of financial intermediation towards productive sectors of the economy. Policymakers, particularly monetary and financial regulatory authorities, should formulate and implement policies that

incentivize commercial banks to expand credit to these growth-enhancing sectors. Such policies may include the strengthening of credit guarantee schemes, implementation of sector-specific refinancing facilities, and the provision of concessionary lending rates to reduce the cost of capital and mitigate lending risks.

Also, the findings underscore the importance of deepening financial sector development through enhanced financial inclusion and improved access to credit, especially for small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) operating within agriculture, manufacturing, and export value chains. Addressing structural rigidities such as stringent collateral requirements, information asymmetry, and weak credit infrastructure will enhance the efficiency of credit delivery and utilization. In addition, there is a compelling case for the adoption of selective credit control measures and targeted macroprudential policies aimed at ensuring optimal allocation of financial resources. Regulatory frameworks that promote sectoral lending quotas or provide incentives for priority sector financing could further reinforce the growth-inducing effects of bank credit. The results also imply that financial sector policies should be complemented by supportive fiscal and structural policies. Investment in critical infrastructure, enhancement of export promotion mechanisms, and the creation of an enabling business environment are essential to maximize the productivity of credit and sustain its positive impact on economic growth.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study provides empirical evidence that commercial bank lending to the agricultural, manufacturing, and export sectors exerts a positive and statistically significant influence on Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) in Nigeria, thereby affirming the critical role of sectoral credit allocation in driving economic growth. The findings underscore the importance of a well-functioning financial intermediation system that efficiently channels funds to productive sectors of the economy. Consequently, sustained policy efforts aimed at enhancing access to credit, improving the efficiency of credit delivery, and creating an enabling macroeconomic and institutional environment are essential for maximizing the growth-enhancing potential of bank lending. Overall, prioritizing sector-specific financing within a stable economic framework remains pivotal to achieving sustainable and inclusive economic development in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the empirical findings, the following recommendations are advanced:

Agricultural sector loan → RGDP (positive and significant): Policymakers should strengthen and expand agricultural credit schemes by enhancing existing intervention programmes, introducing targeted credit guarantees, and providing concessionary interest rates. In addition, improving rural financial infrastructure and supporting value-chain financing will ensure that increased credit translates into higher agricultural productivity and output growth.

Manufacturing sector loan → RGDP (positive and Non-significant): Government and regulatory authorities should promote increased bank lending to the manufacturing sector through fiscal incentives, tax reliefs, and subsidized financing windows. Complementary policies aimed at improving

power supply, transportation infrastructure, and industrial capacity utilization are essential to maximize the growth impact of manufacturing credit.

Export sector loan → RGDP (positive and significant): There is a need to incentivize export financing by establishing export credit facilities, strengthening export financing institutions, and ensuring exchange rate stability. Policies that promote export diversification, reduce trade barriers, and enhance global competitiveness will further amplify the positive contribution of export sector credit to economic growth.

Overall, a coordinated policy framework that encourages sector-specific credit expansion, supported by structural and macroeconomic stability measures, is recommended to sustain and enhance Nigeria's economic growth trajectory.

CONTRIBUTION TO KNOWLEDGE

Empirical contribution to sectoral finance–growth nexus: The study extends the existing literature by providing disaggregated empirical evidence on the impact of commercial bank credit to specific real sectors agriculture, manufacturing, and exports on economic growth in Nigeria. Unlike aggregate credit studies, it demonstrates that sector-specific lending exerts a positive and statistically significant effect on RGDP, thereby offering a more nuanced understanding of how financial intermediation drives growth through distinct productive channels.

Methodological and policy relevant insight: The study contributes methodologically by operationalizing sectoral credit variables as separate growth determinants, thereby improving model specificity and reducing aggregation bias common in prior studies. This approach generates clearer policy insights, highlighting the relative importance of targeted credit allocation in stimulating economic growth and providing an evidence-based foundation for sector-focused financial and macroeconomic policy formulation in Nigeria.

JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

The justification for this study derives first from the central problem of persistent low and unstable economic growth in Nigeria, despite sustained expansion in the banking sector and various credit intervention programmes targeted at the real sector. This paradox raises concerns regarding the effectiveness and allocation of commercial bank credit in stimulating productive activities. Second, there exists a notable knowledge gap in the literature, as most prior studies have focused on aggregate bank credit, thereby masking the differential impact of sector specific lending on economic growth. Limited empirical attention has been given to disaggregating Bank loans into key productive sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and exports within the Nigerian context. This study addresses this gap by providing a sectoral analysis of commercial bank lending and its impact on Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP). Consequently, the study contributes to knowledge by offering empirical evidence on the relative importance of sectoral credit allocation and by improving methodological precision through disaggregation, thereby generating more targeted and policy-relevant insights for enhancing economic growth in Nigeria.

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APPENDIX 1

YEAR	RGDP	AGRSL	MFRSL	EXPSL	REER
2000	22,269.98	41.03	141.29	25.31	64.41
2001	28,662.47	55.85	206.89	34.53	72.67
2002	32,995.38	59.85	233.47	26.71	91.60
2003	39,157.88	62.10	294.31	34.47	128.87
2004	44,285.56	67.74	332.11	31.35	137.72
2005	54,612.26	48.56	352.04	26.43	138.05
2006	62,980.40	49.39	445.79	52.69	150.91
2007	71,713.94	149.58	487.58	66.55	154.29
2008	80,092.56	106.35	932.80	75.19	87.89
2009	89,043.62	135.70	993.46	45.87	97.25
2010	94,144.96	128.41	987.64	44.81	94.51
2011	101,489.49	255.21	1,053.21	36.18	85.49
2012	113,711.63	316.36	1,068.34	65.61	77.01
2013	22,269.98	343.70	1,179.69	3.93	71.82
2014	28,662.47	478.91	1,647.45	1,045.19	68.54
2015	32,995.38	449.31	1,736.19	985.69	66.70
2016	39,157.88	525.95	2,215.74	984.90	87.97
2017	44,285.56	528.24	2,171.37	1,023.78	99.37
2018	54,612.26	610.15	2,230.15	1,076.72	86.67
2019	62,980.40	772.38	2,622.54	1,247.37	78.98
2020	71,713.94	1,049.68	3,191.37	1,343.59	79.15
2021	80,092.56	1,457.82	4,089.29	1,708.38	73.07
2022	89,043.62	1,812.47	5,566.43	2,214.41	86.67
2023	94,144.96	2,255.36	7,732.46	3,548.74	78.98
2024	101,489.49	2,854.51	2,854.51	4,536.64	79.15
2025	113,711.63	2,854.51	2,854.51	4,536.64	73.07

SOURCES; CBN DATA 2025